

**AN APPRAISAL OF DATABASE SECURITY IN A BUSINESS ORGANIZATION
(CASE STUDY: FINTRAK SOFTWARE COMPANY LIMITED)**

CN – 7000 - 46011

JOSEPH BENEDICT

user12148544

MENTAL WEALTH; PROFESSIONAL LIFE (DISSERTATION) (46011)

**A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS OF THE SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE, COMPUTING, AND
ENGINEERING - ACE, AT THE UNIVERSITY OF EAST LONDON, UNITED
KINGDOM, FOR THE DEGREE OF MASTER OF SCIENCE IN INFORMATION
SECURITY AND DIGITAL FORENSICS.**

APRIL, 2023

TITLE PAGE

AN APPRAISAL OF DATABASE SECURITY IN A BUSINESS ORGANIZATION

(CASE STUDY: FINTRAK SOFTWARE COMPANY LIMITED)

BY

JOSEPH OLUWASEUN BENEDICT

A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
OF THE SCHOOL OF ARCHITECTURE, COMPUTING, AND ENGINEERING - ACE, THE
UNIVERSITY OF EAST LONDON, UNITED KINGDOM, FOR THE DEGREE OF MASTER
OF SCIENCE IN INFORMATION SECURITY AND DIGITAL FORENSICS.

CERTIFICATION

This work has been supervised and approved as having satisfied the requirement for the award of a Master M.Sc. (Hons) in Information Security and Digital Forensic, at The School of Architecture, Computing, And Engineering (ACE), University of East London, United Kingdom.

Olumide Babatope Longe Mr.

Date

Project Supervisor

DEDICATION

This project work is dedicated to the Almighty God, the author, and finisher of my faith.

To my beloved Mother whose memory continues to live on in my HEART.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Special thanks to the Almighty God, My Creator, Provider, Protector, and Guardian, with a grateful heart, I say a big thank you to God for the grace and privilege accorded me to complete this program. Great is thy faithfulness.

I appreciate my wonderful and loving wife, Mrs. Angelina Y. Benedict, I could not have made it this far without her tireless effort, care, moral, and emotional support. Words cannot express my gratitude. I am grateful. And to my son, Emmanuel O. Benedict, thank you for your understanding, cooperation, and prayers, you will attain greater heights in the name of Jesus, Amen.

ABSTRACT

Security today is one of the most important and challenging tasks people face in every aspect of their lives. Databases are complex, and many database security Professionals need to understand risk and security issues related to different databases. Even with full knowledge of the database assets, databases are harder to secure because there are unique implementations and procedures for databases. Database security uses a wide range of data security controls to protect databases against any attacks (internal or external).

Considering the amount of data stored in a database and the importance of that data for any organization, the organization must secure the data in the database. With the increase in the number of reported cases of data breaches, cybercrime, exposure of sensitive information, disclosure of confidential data to unauthenticated users, and data intrusion, there is a need for industries dependent on Databases to ensure their data security and to defend their data from all these security threats.

In today's world, data is generated rapidly, and the final destination of such data is the database. These data are stored in the database for easy and efficient management. All the operations of data manipulation and maintenance are done using Database Management System. Considering the importance of data in an organization, securing the data in the database is essential. A secure database is reciprocated from different possible database attacks, and security models are required to develop databases.

These models are different in many aspects as they deal with different database security issues. They may also be different because they make different assumptions about what constitutes a secure database. The history of database research backs more than 30 Years which created the concept of the rationale behind database systems that have become the most fundamental change in an organization's strategic technology. The organization must ensure that its information and data are secured and confidential. Therefore, they deployed systems or application functions, services, and tools for data maintenance and management packed into the so-called Relational Database Management System (RDMS). Such functions contain Services plus privileges for authorization to keep legitimate users (authorized) to access the database.

Database security means disallowing illegitimate users to access the database and its sensitive information, whether unintentionally or accidentally. Therefore, most firms consider possible threats as measures to their database system. Now there is a greater emphasis on database security than in the past as the amount of data stored in the corporate database is increasing, and people depend more on the corporate data for decision-making, customer service management, supply chain management, and so much more. Any loss or unavailability of corporate data will cripple today's organization and seriously affect its performance. Now the unavailability of the database for a few minutes could result in severe losses to the organization. The organization should identify all the risk factors and weak elements from the database security perspective and find solutions to counter and neutralize each threat.

To remove security threats, every organization must have a security policy that would be implemented. In security policy, authentication plays a vital role because if authentication is proper, then there are fewer chances of threats. Different users have different access rights to different database objects. Access Control Mechanisms deal with managing access rights. It is the essential technique to protect the data objects in the databases and is supported by most DBMS.

This study focuses on an appraisal of database security in a business environment, a case study of Fintrak Software Company Limited.

Key Words: Database, Security, Database Security, Business Organization

Word Count: 586

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TITLE PAGE	i
CERTIFICATION	ii
DEDICATION	iii
AKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iv
ABSTRACT	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS	viii

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the study	1
1.2. Statement of the Problem	3
1.3. Aims and Objectives of the Study	4
1.4. Research Questions	5
1.5. Significance of the Study	6
1.6. Scope and Restrictions of the Study	6
1.7. Theoretical Framework	6
1.8. Operational Definitions of Terms	8

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0. Introduction	9
--------------------------	----------

2.1.	Concept of Database Security	9
2.2.	Security Threats	10
2.3.	The Database as the Heart Information System	11
2.4.	Database Fundamentals	12
2.5.	Database as the Base of Business Organizations	12
2.6.	Cloud Computing Components	18
2.7.	Rational Database Security	17
2.8.	Database Security Trends	19

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.0.	Methodology	26
3.1.	Research Design	26
3.2.	Design of Descriptive Research	27
3.3.	Study Population	27
3.4.	Sampling Techniques	28
	3.4.1. Non-probability Sampling	29
3.5.	Method for Data Collection	30
3.6.	Method of Data Analysis	30

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.0. Introduction	32
4.1. Data Analysis	33
4.2. The Liker Scale	34
4.3. Demographic Data	35
4.4. Bio-Data Information	36
4.5. Presentation and Discussion of Research Questions	36
4.6. Data Interpretation	39

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Summary of the findings	42
5.2. Conclusion	43
5.3. Recommendations	44
5.4. Suggestion	45

REFERENCES	47
-------------------	-----------

APPENDIXES

QUESTIONNAIRE

Appendix I	55
-------------------	-----------

Appendix II	56
--------------------	-----------

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

In a crisis, technology has greatly increased our odds of surviving and enhanced our ability to learn, live, travel, communicate, and survive. Life would be impossible without the technology utilized in the fundamental infrastructure that supports our daily activities, which is quickly becoming a necessity (Ghafir et al., 2013). Businesses may now improve the efficiency of their operations and expand their capacities thanks to the availability of data's generated. .

Data has altered how the twenty-first century seems because of its capacity to result in breakthroughs. In the present era, data is now a strategic asset of utmost importance, ranging from an individual who keeps track of his monthly spending to a company looking to increase income through data mining. Akanji et al. (2014) however emphasized that these developments bring a slew of security risks, such as hostile persons targeting databases, servers and storages to alter data integrity, illegally access data, and, finally, leaking sensitive and critical organizations' data to the outside world.

A database is a collection of data tied to one another and contains all the information relevant to an organization. The majority of people perform at least one database-related task each day, making databases and database systems crucial to modern life. According to Malik, et al. (2016), anyone could store data and information into a database to protect business asset. Based on the sensitive nature of data stored in a database, the database must be secured. Database security protects data against unauthenticated usage, unexpected errors, data loss and corruption, and any other undesired action on the database (Deepika, 2015).

All database layers should to be secure by several data security controls (Emil B., 2009).The quality, amount, and level of security of every organization's database determine its chances of success and failure. The data containing the organization's database is one of the crucial assets that must be protected, just like every other company asset. Physical, endpoints, network, application, and host layers are among the various levels that need to be safeguarded to keep in databases secure.

Cyber-attacks are becoming increasingly sophisticated as technology advances, and it is essential to be vigilant to spot evolving cyber threats as most businesses face a complex problem in remaining competitive in the face of cyber threats. It is therefore important that businesses strengthen their database security procedures in order to function correctly, and this requires a deliberate effort to protect an organization's data from threats like accidental or intentional loss, destruction, or misuse. The risks provide a barrier to the company regarding data access and integrity. Both actual loss—like hardware theft—and intangible loss—like a decline in confidence in the organization's actions—can be dangerous. To address the current issues, proper security measures must be implemented and intellectual data must be protected for businesses to exist in today's globally connected world.

The primary goal of database security is to safeguard and preserve information and data against unauthorized access. This can be achieved using various techniques such as encryption and similar technologies to secure the database from unauthorized access. Today's databases and information technology infrastructure are frequently vulnerable to several security threats. Many of these threats are present in small firms, but susceptibility is significant in large businesses and institutions because they hold sensitive information that many persons and departments use (Paul & Aithal, 2019, pp. 53-58). Well-functioning organizations restrict access to their data, servers, and documents for unauthorized individuals, unlicensed programs, and software in an effort to protect the security of their databases. They also ensured no accidental or deceptive variances in data, applications, or software deployed within the organizations infrastructure (Teimoor, 2021, pp. 38–46).

Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability (CIA Triad) are the three fundamental characteristics of database security. It is a paradigm developed to build security rules to recognize possible risks and the necessary remedies to assure information security. Any data security solution is only complete if it meets all three criteria:

Confidentiality: means assuring data privacy, and safeguarding stored data against fraudulent and unauthorized access. It is implemented in the database using an access control system that enforces multiple degrees of access and encryption mechanisms on the database (Swati & Dimple, 2020)

Integrity: means that only authorized users should be allowed to make modifications to the database. Database integrity includes maintaining the data's correctness, consistency, and trustworthiness (Swati & Dimple, 2020). These is achieved by combining access control with database integrity restrictions

Availability: means that information is easily accessible whenever required, and it is feasible by rigorously maintaining and providing redundancies for all of the database's hardware, software, access routes, and mechanical components (Swati & Dimple, 2020).

Furthermore, database security permits or prohibits users from executing tasks on the database. Database managers in a company assess dangers and develop procedures to reduce any risks. Controls employing passwords and usernames to control people who access databases are examples of such operations. The system built is known as a database management security system, and it stores user information and provides access when passwords and usernames are given (Singh & Rai, 2014, pp. 3215-3219).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

As technology advances, databases store more than ever, making data the most critical element of database security (Gupta et al., 2019). Cyber-attacks on databases are on the rise, posing a significant threat to businesses and organizations, as confidential and sensitive data can be exposed, tampered with, or stolen. Inadequate data protection is the primary threat factor, which includes data exposure, data tempering, and data monitoring or collection (Sharma et al., 2018).

Since databases form the backbone of any business, organizations must install a comprehensive security solution to prevent unauthorized access to their databases, whether intentional or unintentional. A security breach can have significant consequences, such as financial loss, reputational damage, and legal repercussions. Therefore, robust security measures, such as encryption, firewalls, and access control, must be implemented to protect the database from potential cyber-attacks (Gupta et al., 2019)

Despite the growing importance of database security, many organizations struggle to remain competitive while safeguarding against evolving cyber threats. Cyber-attacks are becoming increasingly sophisticated, and staying alert and detecting developing cyber threats is crucial. Research has shown that organizations that prioritize database security have a competitive edge and are more likely to withstand cyber-attacks.

To address the growing concerns related to database security in commercial business organizations, this study explored the various elements influencing database security, including organizational culture, security policies, and security infrastructure. By identifying these elements, organizations can better understand the importance of database security and implement effective security measures to protect their databases from potential cyber-attacks.

1.3 Aims and Object of the Study

The inherent risks associated with databases make it imperative to address the issue of database security systematically and comprehensively. This study was directed toward achieving four primary aims, which are critical for ensuring the security and protection of organizational databases.

Firstly, this study identified the risks associated with databases within corporate organizations. This includes a thorough analysis of the potential risks and vulnerabilities that databases are exposed to and an assessment of the impact of such risks on the organization.

Secondly, the study determined the necessity for database authentication, a critical aspect of database security. Authentication mechanisms such as passwords and access controls can help to prevent unauthorized access to databases and mitigate risks.

Thirdly, the study verified the issues that pose a threat to database security. This includes an analysis of the various threats that databases face, including data breaches, hacking, and insider threats, among others. The study will also explore the impact of such threats on the organization and its operations.

Finally, the study investigated methods to assure maximum data protection for organizational databases. This includes an exploration of various security measures and best practices that can be implemented to enhance database security and reduce the risks associated with database usage.

Overall, this study provided a comprehensive understanding of the various factors that influence database security within corporate organizations and to provide practical solutions and recommendations for enhancing database security and protection.

1.4 Research Questions

Research questions are a critical aspect of research design, as they help to focus the study and provide a framework for data collection and analysis. According to Creswell (2009), research questions are explicitly stated questions designed to address the study's specific objectives and provide guidance for the research process. They are typically formulated based on the research problem or gap in knowledge that the study sort to address. As such, they are closely aligned with the research objectives and provide a clear and concise statement of the purpose of the study. Research questions can be broad or specific, depending on the scope and focus of the study.

The formulation of research questions requires careful consideration and planning, as they must be relevant, feasible, and answerable through the available data and research methods. In addition, research questions must be specific enough to provide clear guidance for data collection and analysis and flexible enough to allow new insights and unexpected findings to emerge (Creswell, 2009).

Research questions are essential for conducting rigorous and meaningful research, as they provide a clear direction for the study and help to ensure that the research process is focused and purposeful. By explicitly stating the research questions, researchers can demonstrate the significance of the study and contribute to the advancement of knowledge in their field of inquiry. The following research questions were utilized to reach the goal of this study:

- What are the risks involved with databases in businesses?

- What is the purpose of database authentication?
- What variables influence database security?
- How can the database's greatest security be ensured?

1.5 Significance of the Study

Based on the sensitivity and critical nature of the information in the database, an organization must guard it diligently. As a result, this paper assessed the current database security issues.

The research will also aid in the development of database security capabilities by assisting corporate businesses in identifying and recruiting key and skilled individuals to handle the databases element of their corporation.

The research will also provide the corporate organization with a powerful answer for dealing with database security concerns.

1.6 Scope and Restrictions of the Study

This study aimed to evaluate database security in a corporate company. Because it is impossible to analyze all commercial groups, the research restricts itself to Fintrak Software Company Limited, and the restriction was caused by time and work restrictions.

1.7 Theoretical Framework

Theories are formal collections of ideas that attempt to explain how research or anything is founded. They are used to explain and predict behavior, events, or phenomena logically and systematically. Theories provide a framework for understanding and interpreting research findings and can guide the development of new research questions and hypotheses.

Theories are based on empirical evidence and are constantly refined and updated as new evidence becomes available. They provide a foundation for scientific inquiry and help researchers to develop testable hypotheses and to design studies that can empirically test those hypotheses.

In social sciences, theories can be used to explain social phenomena such as human behavior, social interactions, cultural norms, and institutions. They can also be used to guide the development of interventions or policies to address social issues and problems.

In summary, theories provide a logical basis for research by organizing and explaining phenomena and guiding the development of new research questions and hypotheses. They are an important tool for researchers in social sciences and other fields, as they provide a framework for understanding and interpreting research findings. Additionally, A theory is a collection of logically organized principles or connections that define a field and strive to elucidate a problem, characterize revolutionary parts of a phenomenon, or systematically give predictive utility (Stam, 2007).

Theory of Computational Complexity

The field of computation theory seeks to develop a viable theory that deals with the quantitative elements of computation and constructs a broad theory that investigates the features of possible measures of the difficulty of computing functions. Computational complexity theory is a subfield of computation theory that focuses on assessing the inherent difficulty of solving computational problems (Meseguer & Montanari, 1990). It categorizes problems based on their intrinsic difficulty and connects those classes.

In computational complexity theory, a *computational problem* is defined as a task that a computer can theoretically solve, which is equivalent to saying that a mechanical application of mathematical procedures, such as an algorithm can solve the problem. The theory introduces mathematical models of computing to analyze the difficulty of problems and quantify the resources required to solve them, such as time and storage. The worst-case complexity of computing problems is the primary emphasis of complexity theory, as it helps determine the practical boundaries of what computers can and cannot perform (Arora & Boaz, 2009).

One of the key metrics of computational complexity is time complexity, which assesses the time required to solve a problem. Time complexity classes such as P, NP, NP-hard, NP-complete, and EXPTIME are classes used to categorize problems based on their intrinsic difficulty. Space complexity is another important metric that assesses the memory required to solve a problem. PSPACE, NPSPACE, PSPACE-hard, and PSPACE-complete are examples of space complexity classes (Yan, 1998, pp. 155-156). Investigating the computational complexity of a problem can reveal whether an efficient solution algorithm exists for the problem.

Computational complexity theory also covers other complexity metrics, including communication complexity, circuit complexity, and parallel computing. It plays a significant role in determining the practical limitations of what computers can and cannot accomplish. A critical distinction between algorithm analysis and computational complexity theory is that the former is concerned with analyzing the number of resources required by a specific algorithm to solve a problem. In contrast, the latter is concerned with all possible algorithms that could be used to solve the same problem (Arora & Boaz, 2009).

In conclusion, computational complexity theory is a subfield of computation theory that seeks to categorize and assess the inherent difficulty of computational problems based on their resource requirements. It plays a crucial role in determining the practical limitations of what computers can and cannot accomplish.

1.8 Definition of Terms

- a. **Appraisal:** This is an act of assessing something or someone
- b. **Database:** Is an organized collection of structured information or data typically stored electronically in a computer system.
- c. **Security:** This is the state of being free from danger or threats
- d. **Business Organization:** An entity formed to carry on commercial enterprises.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

A literature review provides a comprehensive overview and critical analysis of the existing research and knowledge on a particular topic or issue. It aims to identify gaps, inconsistencies, and contradictions in the literature and helps researchers to develop research questions and hypotheses. Literature reviews are essential in any academic discipline as they provide a foundation for research and help researchers to build on existing knowledge. They can also be used to demonstrate a research project's novelty and significance and support a study's theoretical and methodological framework.

Literature reviews serve as the foundation for research in every academic discipline. A literature review compiles and evaluates the research on a specific topic or concern one is researching and writing about. According to Chris (2018), a literature review summarizes and interprets findings from academic books, articles, or journals on a specific topic.

As a result, this chapter provides a survey of the literature on the subject of this study.

The literature on challenges influencing database security in a business environment is specifically examined in this chapter. A substantial quantity of work is covered in this area, allowing us to check and use the sources listed below.

2.1 Concept of Database Security

Database security challenges have become more sophisticated due to the extensive use of distributed client/server architecture instead of mainframe systems. Databases are a firm's primary resource; thus, rules and processes must be implemented to ensure the security and integrity of their data. Furthermore, because of the internet and intranets, access to the database has become more widespread, raising the risks of illegal access (Singh & Rai, 2014, pp. 3215-3219).

Database security aims to keep the database safe from accidental or purposeful loss. These threats jeopardize the data's integrity and dependability. Furthermore, database security permits or prohibits users from executing tasks on the database. Database

managers in a company assess dangers and develop procedures to reduce risks and implement controls such as passwords and usernames to user access to the databases. The system built is known as a database management security system, and it stores user information and provides access when passwords and usernames are given (Singh & Rai, 2014, pp. 3215-3219).

In their work, Pevnev and Kapchynskiy (2018) attempt to illustrate the notion of data security by presenting a complete collection of rules and actions that may limit the risks associated with violations of data confidentiality, integrity, and availability. It also covered several vulnerabilities when existing databases and database management systems are used. Implementing the supplied guidance while designing, administering, and utilizing databases will assist in avoiding the effect of the associated database risks. Various insider hazards, in particular, occupy a sizable niche in the list of database threats.

2.2 Security Threats

According to IBM's 2019 Data Breach Report, performed by the Ponemon Institute, the cost of a data breach has climbed by 12% over the last five years and is currently \$3.92 million on a global scale (Chris Brook, 2022). The economic effects of database hacks are immediate and often last for years after the occurrence (Tresorit Team, 2019). A study by Swati & Dimple (2020) identified several security threats that results in data breaches, and this threats have topped the risk assessment of database security in the last decade:

a. Abuse of Excessive and Inappropriate Privileges: Database management systems and the accompanying data structures are complex; thus, administrators provide users exorbitant privileges to prevent any application failure brought on by an insufficient set of rights (White Paper, 2016). When users are granted greater rights than are necessary for their job tasks, these privileges might be abused. This permission can be abused to influence the grades of any student or course. This abuse occurs as a result of offering general access permissions to a specific set of users even though it surpasses their unique work needs (Singh & Rai, 2014, pp. 3215-3219)

b. Lawful Privilege Abuse: This occurs when their job functions grant a person only the privileges necessary and then use these legitimate privileges for unauthorized reasons. Due to their work needs, user groups such as Database System Administrators (DBA) and Developers have access to the whole database (White Paper, 2016). If a DBA attempts to access database data directly rather than through the application interface, all application permissions and security controls are bypassed, paving the route for power abuse (Nedhal & Dana, 2013).

c. Privilege Elevation: Users with low-level privileges may exploit database vulnerabilities to elevate their access rights to high-level privileges. This can result in unauthorized users accessing important information (Deepika, 2015).

d. Platform Vulnerabilities: Any flaws in the underlying operating system, such as Windows 2000, Windows XP, or Linux, can result in privilege escalation, denial of service, data corruption, and unauthorized access security concerns (Singh & Rai, 2014, pp. 3215-3219). For example, a possible security vulnerability in Intel WIFI Drivers and Intel PROSet/Wireless Wi-Fi Software extension DLL was addressed in the November 2019 platform update Intel memory corruption problems (R). WIFI Drivers before version 21.40 may allow a privileged user to enable privilege escalation, denial of service, and information exposure through local access.

e. Inadequate Audit Trails: Every database deployment should include automated recording of all sensitive data transactions. Failure to monitor transactions and collect audit information on database activity puts the organization in danger on several fronts. Many businesses rely on database-provided native audit tools; however, these tools do not collect enough contextual information to assure security, identify threats, and offer event forensics.

Another reason native audit tools are untrustworthy is that users with valid or escalated administrator access can disable database auditing to conceal criminal activity (Akanji et al, 2014). To achieve a solid separation of duties, policy, database responsibilities, and audit capabilities should be separated from the database server platform and administrator (Malik & Patel, 2016).

f. DoS (Denial of Service): This is a broad category attack in which legitimate users, such as workers, members, or account holders, are denied access to database services

or resources. This is accomplished by shutting down the system or network, rendering it unreachable to its intended users (Mahjabin et al., 2017).

This may be accomplished in two ways: by overwhelming the destination with traffic or by delivering information that causes a crash (Singh & Rai, 2014, pp. 3215-3219). Even if they do not immediately result in data theft, loss, or corruption, they can be time and money-consuming to resolve.

g. Unsecured Storage Media: Backup storage media is frequently less secure than other database assets. This results from multiple high-profile data breaches in which database backup tapes and hard drives were stolen or accidentally exposed. Many rules require the protection of backup copies of sensitive data, and encrypting all backup data is one possible solution to this problem (Nedhal & Dana, 2013).

2.3 The Database as the Heart Information System

Juma & Makupi (2017) described databases as the core of Information Systems (IS); hence maintaining database quality is crucial to ensuring IS quality. Determining what defines a good database model or architecture has recently proven tricky. As a result, in their discussion, they measured specific traits and components of the database installation. In a similarly study by Mousa et al. (2020), they revealed that due to the sensitivity and worth of the data, attackers would prefer to target the database because it can be corrupted in a variety of ways. Therefore, they suggested that the database be protected against intrusions and threats. Most of the attacks documented in this investigation are solvable; some of the assaults are genuine, while others are not.

According to Sarmah (2019), database security is critical and impacts the company's economic activity and public faith in the government. This survey also revealed that internal personnel account for around 25% of the events, with the loss or theft of various equipment accounting for the other 50%. This article explains the notion of a penetration database and how to verify compliance. The survey opined that both strategic and technological security steps should be considered to ensure strong database security.

2.4 Database Fundamentals

Paul and Aithal (2019) in their article addressed the foundations of databases, such as their meaning, features, and responsibilities, focusing on various database security challenges. Furthermore, this article covers security management fundamentals as well as essential technology. Consequently, many aspects of database security have been briefly explored in this article.

Historically, many data protection professionals in the industry and government, according to these writers, were unfamiliar with the technology. Following major terrorist attacks, the government considers and, in many cases, implements private restricting rules because they believe that giving up a little privacy for increased protection is worth it, even if it means giving up some privacy. While concentrating too much on Cyber security, this is just the beginning.

2.5 Database as the Base of Business Organizations

In the modern business environment, data is a critical asset that can be used to gain a competitive advantage and drive business growth (Coronel, Morris, & Rob, 2016). However, managing and analyzing large amounts of data can be challenging, especially for businesses with complex operations and multiple data sources. This is where databases become a foundational tool for managing and leveraging data in business organizations.

A database is a structured collection of data that is organized in a way that allows for efficient storage, retrieval, and management (Elmasri & Navathe, 2015, p. 5). Databases are used to store various types of data, such as customer information, financial data, inventory data, and more. By using a database as the base of their operations, businesses can achieve several key benefits:

Centralized Data Management: With a database, businesses can store all their data in one centralized location, making it easier to manage and maintain (Halpin & Morgan, 2008). This can help eliminate data silos and reduce the risk of errors and inconsistencies when data is spread across multiple sources.

Improved Data Quality: By using a database to manage their data, businesses can ensure that their data is accurate, consistent, and up-to-date. Databases offer a range of tools and features, such as data validation and error checking, that can help to improve data quality.

Efficient Data Retrieval: With a database, businesses can retrieve data quickly and easily, even when dealing with large amounts of data. Databases are designed to optimize data retrieval and storage, enabling complex queries and analysis in real time.

Better Decision-Making: By leveraging the data stored in their databases, businesses can gain insights into customer behavior, market trends, and operational performance (Kimball & Ross, 2013). This can help to inform better decision-making and drive business growth.

Overall, databases are an essential tool for managing and leveraging data in modern business organizations. Businesses can use a database as the base of their operations to improve their efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making capabilities and gain a competitive advantage in their industry.

According to Sivananda et al. (2014), databases are the foundation of many applications today and are a significant storage type for many companies. They are a crucial component of many applications, serving as the foundation upon which data-driven processes are built. With an effective database, storing, managing, and accessing the large amounts of data needed to support complex applications can be more accessible.

Saurabh & Siddhaling (2012) argue that databases serve as the foundation for the majority of modern applications, stating that "databases are one of the most important components of a software application" (p.7). They note that "databases provide the storage and retrieval of data, which is the main purpose of an application" (p.7).

In this sense, databases are the backbone of applications, providing the underlying infrastructure to store and manage data for millions of business across the globe. They enable the processing of large amounts of data quickly and accurately, which is essential for applications that require real-time data processing and analysis.

Overall, Saurabh & Siddhaling (2012) findings highlight the central role of databases in modern applications and underscore the importance of effective database design and

management in achieving business success. Because the database includes sensitive and secret information, there is a risk of assault. This study discusses several database hacks and effective database security strategies such as access control, SQLIA approaches, encryption, and data scrambling is covered. The research findings also mentioned several potential future research areas in database security.

According to Singh and Rai (2014), databases form the cornerstone of modern applications and principal storage solution for enterprises. As a result, database assaults are on the rise, but they are particularly dangerous because they provide the invader access to sensitive data. This study looked at a range of database attacks and also assesses relevant database security solutions with possible database protection analysis. This research will lead to a more specific approach to the database security problem.

Privacy-preserving data sharing: As more organizations look to share data with partners or third-party providers, there is a growing need for technologies that enable secure and privacy-preserving data sharing. This may involve developing new encryption or anonymization techniques to protect sensitive information while allowing for practical analysis (Wang et al., 2022).

Cloud database security: With the increasing adoption of cloud-based database systems, research is needed into the unique security challenges posed by these environments. This may include investigating the efficacy of different access control mechanisms or exploring new techniques for detecting and responding to threats (Hashemi et al., 2013).

Blockchain-based database security: As blockchain technology evolves, there is a growing interest in its potential applications for securing databases. This may involve exploring smart contracts or other blockchain-based mechanisms for ensuring data integrity and preventing unauthorized access (Tian et al., 2020).

Machine learning-based database security: As the volume of data handled by databases continues to grow, there is a need for automated techniques that can detect and respond to security threats in real-time. Machine learning approaches offer a promising avenue for achieving this goal by enabling systems to learn from past attacks and adapt their defenses accordingly (Liu et al., 2019).

According to Odirichukwu & Asagba (2018), the amount of businesses putting their data online is increasing daily, allowing people worldwide to interact with and change data. More information may be found online, and the number of database security vulnerabilities develops in tandem with the number of websites and services on the internet. Security inbuilt applications are compromised due to a mix of issues, including a lack of security incentives, a short deadline, and web deception. This article provides training on application security testing and a literature survey on twenty database security threats that affect online applications. Control activities that may be performed to avoid these attacks were examined to enhance online security awareness among the general public and application developers.

The work reflects the idea that developers should make every effort to integrate all of the essential functionality and take security precautions while designing applications. Participation is also essential; all developers should be trained in security testing.

Despite establishing adequate security, the leadership and Admin should devise a means for maintaining a constant backup of their database programs available online.

2.6 Cloud Computing Components

According to Lin & Chen (2012), cloud computing has emerged as an emerging approach due to its on-demand service and scalability qualities. Today, the cloud is mainly used for data storage and extensive data or computation-intensive applications. As a result, data security and privacy have become the primary concerns, particularly for business-level data. Similarly, Zhang et al. (2011) thought existing approaches for data security, sharing, storage, and archiving until destruction needed to be revised. Traditional data security approaches often rely on data encryption and access restriction.

Thilina (2022) reviewed using virtual resources in data storage for database users. It also offered information on database security tactics, attack, and privacy risk mitigation procedures. Organizations can use an innovative business model that requires no initial expenditure to store data and information in databases. It also contains information on database security requirements and assets.

This review article discusses the hazards of database security breaches, virus activity on such data, how to handle or mitigate those concerns, and Oracle security database implementation.

A study by Tabrizchi & Rafsanjani (2020) investigated many components of cloud computing and the current security and privacy challenges these systems face. This paper also proposes a new categorization system for contemporary security solutions in this sector. This research also addressed unresolved issues, proposed future options, and introduced several security threats influencing cloud computing services. This article also analyze security challenges confronting cloud companies such as cloud service providers, data owners, and consumers.

2.7 Rational Database Security

Sharma's (2016) paper presented relational database security and security frameworks as examples of how internet application security for explicit database authorization may be created and implemented. Because Relational Database securities are the most common target for attackers, protection associations and substances are considered critical company resources that must be rigorously safeguarded. This study identified the challenges and hazards connected with relational database security, the requirements for relational database set security, and how database relations offer security at different levels.

Imran & Hyder (2009) explored several security challenges and models for various database management systems. Suggested discretionary and required security models for traditional and object-oriented database systems are provided, and there is still no standard for building these security models. The work provided in this paper presents a consolidated perspective of database security by providing a consolidated image of various database security challenges; it may be expanded to define, create, and implement an effective security policy in a database environment. This study's authors investigated security concerns and concepts for several database management systems. The article proposes optional and mandatory security models for conventional databases and object-oriented systems. Despite this, there is no set of guidelines for creating security models. This research offers a consolidated view of a database by

presenting a consolidated picture of various database difficulties. It may be used to create, plan, and implement an effective database security policy.

Gupta and Singh (2013) provide an overview of various security issues in database systems, including data confidentiality, integrity, and availability. The authors explain the importance of securing databases and the consequences of security breaches. The authors also discuss different security measures that can be used to secure databases.

Access control is described as a technique used to limit access to sensitive data in a database. The authors explain that access control can be implemented using different methods, such as RBAC or ABAC.

Encryption is also discussed as a technique to protect sensitive data stored in a database. The authors explain that encryption can be implemented using symmetric or asymmetric encryption algorithms. They also compare encryption algorithms, such as AES, Blowfish, and RSA.

Auditing is described as a technique used to monitor and record activities in a database system. The authors explain that auditing can detect unauthorized access attempts and track changes to the database.

Authentication is another security technique discussed in the paper. The authors explain that authentication ensures that only authorized users can access the database. Different authentication methods, such as username/password and biometric authentication, are described.

Finally, the authors discuss intrusion detection as a technique to detect and prevent unauthorized access to a database. They explain that intrusion detection can be implemented using different methods, such as signature-based or anomaly-based detection.

The importance of database backup and recovery to ensure data availability in case of a security breach or system failure was also emphasized by the authors.

Gupta and Singh (2013) paper provides an overview of various security issues in database systems and discusses different security measures that can be used to mitigate

these issues. This paper can be a helpful resource for researchers and practitioners working in the field of database security.

Shikha & Shanky (2016) provide a detailed discussion of various encryption and decryption techniques that can be used to secure databases. The authors explain the need for encryption in database security and then discuss different encryption techniques, including symmetric and asymmetric encryption and hashing.

Symmetric encryption is described as a technique in which the same key is used for encryption and decryption. The authors explain that symmetric encryption is fast and efficient, but its security depends on the required length and management.

Asymmetric encryption, also known as public-key encryption, is discussed as a technique in which a pair of keys is used for encryption and decryption. The authors explain that asymmetric encryption is more secure than symmetric encryption but is slower and requires more computational resources.

Hashing is also discussed as a technique to protect data integrity in a database. The authors explain that hashing involves converting a message into a fixed-length string of characters and is used to ensure that the data has not been tampered with.

The authors also provide examples of how these encryption and decryption techniques can be implemented in database systems. For example, they describe how a combination of symmetric and asymmetric encryption can secure sensitive data in a database and how hashing can ensure data integrity.

Shikha & Shanky (2016) paper provides a detailed discussion of various encryption and decryption techniques that can be used to secure databases. This paper can be a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners working in the field of database security.

2.8 Database Security Trends

Database security has become an increasingly important concern in recent years due to the proliferation of cyber-attacks and data breaches. In response, researchers and practitioners have developed several new trends and techniques to improve the security of databases. Below is an overview of some of the critical trends in database security.

One significant trend is the use of encryption to protect sensitive data. Encryption can be used to protect data both at rest and in transit. In recent years, there has been a shift towards using more advanced encryption techniques, such as homomorphic encryption, which allows for computations to be performed on encrypted data without decryption. Encryption is a widely used technique to protect sensitive data in databases. Encryption refers to converting plaintext into ciphertext using a mathematical algorithm and a secret key. This makes the data unreadable to anyone who does not have access to the key, thus ensuring its confidentiality.

One of the main advantages of encryption is that it can protect data even if it is stolen or compromised (Kizza, 2017). Encryption can be applied to various data types, including passwords, credit card numbers, and other sensitive information. Additionally, encryption can be implemented at different levels, such as at the application level, database level, or file system level (Oracle, n.d.). Encryption can be implemented using different algorithms, such as Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), Data Encryption Standard (DES), and Blowfish (Abdullah, 2017). The strength of the encryption depends on the length of the key used, the algorithm's complexity, and the plaintext's length.

However, encryption has some limitations. It can increase the processing time required to access and manipulate data, affecting the system's performance (Kizza, 2017). Additionally, if the encryption key is lost or stolen, the data cannot be decrypted, leading to data loss.

Encryption remains an essential technique for protecting sensitive database data despite its limitations. It is often used with other security measures, such as access control and authentication, to provide a multi-layered approach to database security.

Another significant trend is the use of access control to limit the ability of unauthorized users to access sensitive data. Access control can take several forms, including role-based access control, attribute-based access control, and mandatory access control. Access control is a vital security measure used to prevent unauthorized access to sensitive data. It involves limiting the ability of unauthorized users to access data based on their identity, role, and level of authorization. Access control can be implemented at different levels, such as database, application, and user levels.

One of the main benefits of access control is that it can help organizations protect their sensitive data from unauthorized access, thus minimizing the risk of data breaches. For example, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requires organizations to have appropriate access controls in place to protect personal data (GDPR, 2016).

To implement access control, organizations use various methods such as authentication, authorization, and accounting (AAA). Authentication involves verifying the user's identity attempting to access the system, and authorization verifies whether the user has the necessary permission to access the requested data. Accounting involves logging and tracking the user's activity, recording who accessed what data and when.

Access control can be implemented using different models, such as Mandatory Access Control (MAC), Discretionary Access Control (DAC), and Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) (Stallings, 2017). MAC assigns security labels to each user and object in the system and enforces access control based on these labels. DAC allows the owner or administrator to determine who can access a particular object. RBAC grants access to data based on a user's role or job function.

Organizations should also develop and implement access control policies defining who can access data and under what circumstances. These policies should include a robust password policy, multi-factor authentication, and periodic user access reviews. Access control policies should be regularly reviewed and updated to ensure compliance with changing regulations and business needs.

Access control is essential to limit unauthorized access to sensitive data. Organizations should implement access control measures to protect sensitive data, comply with regulations, and ensure data privacy.

A third trend is the use of anomaly detection to identify unusual behavior within a database. Anomaly detection can help to identify potential security breaches and to prevent attacks before they occur. Machine learning algorithms are often used for anomaly detection, as they can analyze large amounts of data and identify patterns that may indicate an attack (Toshniwal et al., 2020). Anomaly detection is a technique used to identify unusual behavior or activities within a database that could indicate a security breach. Anomaly detection can be used in conjunction with other security measures, such as access control and encryption, to provide a more comprehensive security

solution (Chandola et al., 2009). There are several methods of anomaly detection, including statistical analysis, machine learning, and rule-based systems.

Statistical analysis is a method of anomaly detection that involves analyzing the statistical properties of the data in the database. This can include looking at the data's mean, variance, and distribution and comparing it to historical data or expected values. If there is a significant deviation from the expected values, it may indicate an anomaly (Albalawi, 2018).

Machine learning is another anomaly detection method involving training a machine learning model on historical data to identify patterns and anomalies. The model can then be used to detect anomalies in real-time data. Machine learning can be particularly effective for detecting anomalies in large and complex databases (Nassif et al., 2021).

Rule-based systems involve setting rules and thresholds for what is considered normal behavior within the database. Any behavior that falls outside these rules and thresholds is flagged as an anomaly. Rule-based systems can help detect specific types of anomalies or attacks.

Anomaly detection can be beneficial for detecting insider threats, which are often difficult to detect using traditional security measures. Insiders may have legitimate access to the database, but their behavior may be unusual or suspicious. Anomaly detection can help identify these types of threats and alert security personnel to take action (Nassif et al., 2021).

According to (Ashfaq et al. (2022), "Anomaly detection is an important technique for identifying potential security threats in databases." Anomaly detection can be used in conjunction with other security measures to provide a comprehensive security solution.

A fourth trend is the use of blockchain technology to improve the security of databases. Blockchain can be used to create a distributed ledger of transactions, which can help to prevent unauthorized changes to data. In addition, blockchain can be used to create a tamper-proof audit trail of all database activity (Yassine et al., 2022). Blockchain technology can improve database security by leveraging its decentralized nature, immutable records, advanced cryptography, and smart contract capabilities. Here are some of how blockchain technology can be used to improve database security:

Decentralization: The decentralized nature of blockchain technology makes it difficult for attackers to compromise the system. Rather than relying on a central authority, the blockchain is distributed across a network of nodes, each holding a copy of the ledger. This means that even if one or more nodes are compromised, the integrity of the blockchain is maintained. Additionally, the decentralized nature of the blockchain can make it more difficult for attackers to launch a distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attack, as there is no central point of control to target.

Crosby et al. (2016) state, "Blockchain technology provides a secure, decentralized way to store data, allowing parties to transact with each other without the need for a central authority or intermediary." This makes it more secure than traditional centralized databases.

Immutable Records: The immutability of the records kept on the network is one of the main advantages of blockchain technology. Once a transaction is recorded on the blockchain, it cannot be altered or deleted. This provides high security and integrity for the data stored on the blockchain, as unauthorized users cannot tamper with it. Using cryptographic hashes in the blockchain also ensures that any attempts to alter the data are immediately detected.

Swan (2015) notes, "Blockchain technology provides an immutable ledger that no one can alter once the data has been recorded." This makes it an attractive option for storing sensitive data that requires high security.

Cryptography: Blockchain technology uses advanced cryptographic algorithms to secure the data stored on the network. Public-key cryptography is used to ensure that only authorized users can access the data on the blockchain. Each user has a unique public and private key, with the public key used to encrypt the data and the private key used to decrypt it.

As Choudhary (2021) explain, "The cryptographic algorithms used in the blockchain ensure the security of the data stored on the network and that only authorized users can access the data." This provides high security for the data stored on the blockchain.

Smart Contracts: Smart contracts are self-executing contracts that can be programmed to enforce specific rules and conditions. They can be used to automate various security-

related tasks, such as access control and data encryption, which can improve the security of databases. Smart contracts can also be used to create secure multi-party transactions, which can be helpful in industries such as finance and supply chain management.

As Taherdoost (2023) stated, "Smart contracts can be used to automate various security-related tasks, such as access control and data encryption, which can improve the security of databases." This can lead to more efficient and secure business processes.

Finally, there is a growing trend toward using artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to improve database security. AI and ML can be used for various tasks, including anomaly detection, intrusion detection, and predictive modeling (Kshetri, 2020). Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to improve database security have gained momentum recently. According to a report by Market Research Future, the global market for AI in cybersecurity is expected to grow at a CAGR of 29.14% between 2018 and 2023 (1). This section will explore how AI and ML are being used to improve database security.

Identifying anomalous behavior: Machine learning algorithms can be trained to learn a database's normal behavior and detect deviations from that behavior. These algorithms use statistical methods to identify patterns and learn what is normal for a given database. If any unusual activity is detected, the algorithm can flag it as an anomaly and alert security personnel. For example, if a user suddenly starts accessing data they have never accessed, the ML algorithm can flag this as an anomaly and alert the security team. The algorithm can also be used to monitor for changes in data patterns, such as a sudden increase in requests for specific data, which may indicate a potential attack.

Predictive analytics: AI and ML algorithms can be used to analyze large amounts of data to identify patterns and predict potential security threats. This can help security teams to take measures to prevent potential attacks proactively. For example, the system can analyze the data to identify a pattern of activity consistent with a known type of attack. The system can then predict that a security breach is likely to occur and take preventive measures, such as blocking the IP address of the attacker.

Automated security operations: AI and ML can also automate security operations like threat detection, incident response, and vulnerability management. For example, machine learning algorithms can be used to automatically classify and prioritize security alerts based on their severity, allowing security teams to focus their attention on the most critical threats first. The system can also be trained to automatically respond to certain types of threats, such as blocking an IP address or quarantining a device that is exhibiting suspicious behavior.

Using AI and ML in database security can provide organizations with a more proactive and practical approach to detecting and preventing security threats. As AI and ML technologies evolve, we expect to see more sophisticated and effective security solutions that leverage these technologies.

In conclusion, database security is an essential concern in today's digital landscape, and several trends and techniques can be used to improve the security of databases. These include encryption, access control, anomaly detection, blockchain technology, and AI and ML.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURE

3.0 Methodology

Thomas & Nelson (2001) described research methodology as a systematic active inquiry and discovery process through data collection, analysis, and inference to comprehend a specific phenomenon of interest. It entails employing a scientific and systematic method to gather, organize, analyze, and summarize information about a phenomenon to gain knowledge. It is a scientific method of investigation that seeks to prove an explanation and understanding of a phenomenon. This study often focuses on the meaning, concepts, meanings, traits, metaphors, symbols, and descriptions of objects rather than their counts or measurements (Berg, 2009, pp. 101-157)

Research methodology refers to a systematic and scientific process of inquiry aimed at understanding a given phenomenon of interest. It involves techniques and procedures to collect, organize, analyze, and summarize information about the phenomenon. In qualitative research, the focus is often on the meaning, concepts, traits, metaphors, symbols, and descriptions of objects rather than their counts or measurements. Qualitative research aims to understand better the phenomenon being studied rather than quantify it. This type of research involves an active inquiry and discovery process, where the researcher engages with the data to generate insights and new understandings.

The methodology tackles the following aspects: research design, sample strategy, data collection, data preparation, and data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

The research design is the overarching strategy that a researcher chooses to clearly and rationally unite the different parts of the investigation. According to Asemah et al. (2012), research designs are essential to generate a mental image of the structure for obtaining data for further analysis. A research design is a conceptual framework within which research is carried out, and it serves as the template for data gathering, measurement, and analysis (Kothari, 2004).

Research design is a researcher's overall plan or strategy to guide their investigation. It serves as a unifying framework that helps to bring together the different components of a study, such as the research questions, data collection methods, and analysis techniques. A well-planned research design provides a structured and systematic data collection, analysis, and interpretation approach. It ensures that the study is well-executed and that the data collected is relevant and helpful in answering the research questions.

A descriptive qualitative research design was used in this study.

3.2 Design of Descriptive Research

Descriptive research seeks to characterize a phenomenon and its features. This study is primarily concerned with "what" happened, then "how" or "why" it happened. Descriptive research can be helpful in situations where there is little prior knowledge or understanding of a phenomenon or where the goal is to generate new ideas or hypotheses for future research. Data collection methods in descriptive research often include surveys, observations, and content analysis.

In summary, the main objective of descriptive research is to provide a detailed and accurate description of a phenomenon and its features rather than explaining or predicting it. As a result, observation and survey technologies are frequently utilized to collect data (Gall et al., 2006). Data may be collected intuitively in such a study, but it is frequently examined quantitatively using frequencies, percentages, averages, or other statistical analyses to discover correlations. However, qualitative research is more comprehensive and frequently entails gathering data from numerous sources to better understand individual participants, including their ideas, perspectives, and attitudes.

3.3 Study Population

The study population refers to all persons and objects that fall within the scope of the research issue to be investigated (Ohaja, 2003). The population of a study refers to the entire group of individuals or objects that are of interest to the researcher and that fall

within the scope of the research issue being investigated. The population may be defined in various ways, depending on the research question and the specific goals of the study.

For example, suppose the research question is focused on the effects of weak database security measures. In that case, the population may be defined as all businesses with database security vulnerabilities or weak database security measures put in place.

It is important to note that the population is not always synonymous with the target interest group. In some cases, the researcher may focus on a subset of the population, known as the sample, selected to participate in the study. The sample is typically selected to be representative of the population so that the findings from the study can be generalized to the broader population.

Overall, understanding the population is essential for designing a relevant and appropriate study to the research question and ensuring that the findings are generalizable to the broader population of interest.

Similarly, the population of the study is the topic to be investigated to discover a solution to the defined problem. The research population may also be viewed as a complete item that a researcher investigates and draws conclusions. This study's population included employees from Fintrak Software Company Limited, Mobitel Limited, Phinet systems limited, and Ulesson education.

3.4 Sampling Techniques

The importance of sampling in ensuring a systematic or scientific selection of the sample to be researched cannot be overstated. Thus, sampling is a procedure or technique for picking a representative sample of the population for the research (Tejumaiye, 2003). A sample is a population subject who is representative of the entire population. A sample that is not representative of the population in terms of size is insufficient for testing since the results cannot be extrapolated to the population from which it was obtained.

Sampling is defined as the selection of specific individuals or aspects of a population for objective examination or study. Ohaja (2003). According to him, this selection is necessary due to the impracticability of examining the entire population.

Sampling is an essential process in research, as it involves selecting a representative subset of individuals or aspects of the population for study. It is essential because it is usually impractical or impossible to study the entire population of interest, so researchers must use sampling methods to ensure that the sample is representative of the population and can be used to make inferences about the population as a whole.

A well-designed sampling strategy ensures that the sample is selected systematically, without bias, and with a high level of precision. This helps ensure that the study's findings can be generalized to the population, which is essential for making meaningful conclusions and recommendations based on the research.

It's also important to note that the sample size is a critical consideration in sampling. A sample that is too small may not represent the population and may not yield reliable or valid results. Conversely, a sample that is too large may not be necessary and can lead to a waste of resources. Therefore, researchers must carefully consider the appropriate sample size based on the research question and the characteristics of the population being studied.

3.4.1 Non-probability Sampling

Non-probability sampling is used in this investigation—sampling without regard for probability.

Non-probability sampling employs subjective judgment and a handy sample of population units. Non-probability sampling methods reduce the expense of human interview surveys; the resultant samples frequently resemble probability sample data (Vehovar et al., 2016, pp. 329-346).

Purposive non-probability sampling is used in this study. Purposive sampling involves the researcher subjectively selecting subjects. The researcher's judgment is used to make the selection. Respondents are not randomly chosen but based on the interviewer's

discretion. Purposive sampling is also known as selective, judgmental, or subjective sampling. Crossman (2020) non-probability sampling, the selection of participants is not based on random chance, but rather on subjective judgment or convenience. This type of sampling is often used when it is not feasible or practical to use probability sampling methods, or when the research question requires a specific type of participant that may not be easily accessible through probability sampling.

Purposive non-probability sampling, also known as selective or judgmental sampling, involves the researcher selecting participants based on their knowledge, expertise, or relevance to the research question. This type of sampling is often used in qualitative research, where the researcher is interested in gathering in-depth information from a specific group of people who are knowledgeable about the topic of interest.

While non-probability sampling methods can be useful in certain situations, they have limitations. For example, they may be subject to selection bias, where certain types of participants are overrepresented or underrepresented in the sample, which can affect the generalizability of the findings. Therefore, researchers must carefully consider the strengths and weaknesses of different sampling methods and choose the most appropriate method for their research question and population of interest.

3.5 Method for Data Collection

Data collection tools are those that are used to collect data to test hypotheses or answer research questions. (Ojo, 2003).

In this study, the questionnaire was employed as a data-gathering tool. A questionnaire is a document that contains questions and other sorts of items meant to elicit information suitable for analysis (Babbie, 2014). It may also be viewed as a data collection tool, as it asks standard questions that respondents must answer in writing.

3.6 Method for Data Analysis Method

Data were collected and quantitatively examined. A quantitative research approach uses numbers and everything quantifiable to investigate a phenomenon and its relationships

systematically. It describes, forecasts, and regulates a phenomenon by answering questions about the relationship between quantifiable values (Leedy & Jeanne, 2015, pp. 1-408). Statistics are used in quantitative analysis to confirm or refute the researcher's premise and research questions. The Likert scale was employed with this strategy.

The intensity, stability, and direction of respondents' views toward the study topics were measured using a Likert scale. A Likert scale is a rating system that is used to assess attitudes or views.

In quantitative research, data are typically collected and analyzed using numerical or statistical methods. This approach investigates relationships between variables, makes predictions, and tests hypotheses using empirical data.

The Likert scale is a commonly used rating system in quantitative research to measure attitudes, opinions, or perceptions. Respondents are asked to rate their level of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements on a scale, usually ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The scores are then assigned numerical values and analyzed using statistical methods to determine patterns and relationships between variables.

Overall, quantitative research provides a systematic and rigorous approach to investigating phenomena using numerical data and statistical analysis. The Likert scale is a helpful tool for measuring attitudes and perceptions in this type of research.

This scale asks respondents to score an item based on their level of agreement, such as highly agreed, agreed, undecided, disagreed, and strongly disagreed. After the respondents have responded, numbers are assigned to their replies. As an example:

Strongly agreed - 4

Agreed -3

Disagreed -2

Strongly disagreed -1

This allows a researcher to interpret the replies.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.0 Introduction

This chapter deals with the analysis of data analysis and the presentation of results obtained through the application of the procedure described in chapter three. It involves the analysis of the responses and their interpretation. Data analysis and interpretation refer to organizing, cleaning, transforming, and summarizing data collected during the research to draw meaningful conclusions and make informed decisions. Data analysis aims to make sense of the data collected and present it clearly and understandably.

In quantitative research, data analysis typically involves statistical methods such as descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, and regression analysis. Descriptive statistics are used to summarize and describe the basic features of the data. In contrast, inferential statistics are used to draw conclusions about the larger population based on the sample data. Regression analysis models the relationship between variables and makes predictions based on that relationship.

In qualitative research, data analysis involves a more subjective and interpretive approach. It typically involves coding and categorizing data into themes and patterns and interpreting them to generate insights and understanding. Qualitative data analysis may also involve using software tools for organizing and analyzing data.

Regardless of the research approach, data analysis and interpretation are critical steps in the research process as they help identify trends, patterns, and relationships in the data that inform research findings and recommendations. The data analysis and interpretation must be conducted rigorously and systematically to ensure the research results' validity and reliability. Depending on the sort of data you are dealing with and the questions you are attempting to answer, several methodologies and tools are available for data analysis and interpretation.

Examining the data for patterns or discrepancies is one of the initial tasks in data analysis. This may be accomplished through visualizations like histograms, scatter plots, bar charts, and fundamental statistical measurements like mean, median, and standard deviation.

Depending on how the data appears, the data can be cleaned by eliminating missing numbers, outliers, and other issues that may impair the research.

After cleaning the data, you may change it to be more suited for the study you intend to do. This might include standardizing the data, adding new variables, or categorizing the data.

Finally, modeling the data using various statistical and machine-learning approaches to create predictions or draw inferences. This may involve creating a linear regression model to predict a continuous result or training a decision tree to categorize.

There are several tools and applications available. Excel, SAS, R, and Python are examples of data analysis tools and applications. Python has many data analysis and visualization libraries, including pandas, NumPy, sci-kit-learn, TensorFlow, and matplotlib, making it the most popular among data scientists and analysts.

The analysis of the data and subsequent presentation of results were all based on the four research questions formulated for the study.

4.1 Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using statistics with a simple table and a Likert 5-point rating scale. The simple Table was used to determine the frequency rate and percentage of respondents' demography.

Example 1.

ITEM	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
FEMALE	RESPONDENT NUMBERS	X

Source: Field study (2023).

4.2 The Likert Scale

A Likert scale is a rating scale used to measure attitudes or opinions. A Likert scale typically consists of a series of statements about a topic. Respondents are asked to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with each statement on a scale, usually ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." The scores from the individual items are often combined to create an overall score or index representing the respondent's attitude or opinion on the topic. Once the respondents have answered, numbers are ascribed to the responses or example:

Strongly Agreed 4

Agreed. 3

Disagreed 2

Strongly Disagreed. 1

This Table has its codes and values as shown in the Table below, where

SA= Strongly Agreed

S= Agreed

D= Disagreed

SD= Strongly Disagreed

Example 2:

CODE	SA	A	D	SD
VALUE	4	3	2	1

Source: Field survey (2023).

To obtain the criteria mean of these variables, the total value is summed up to get fifteen (15), which is divided by the number of the variables, which is five (5), to give 3.0. This (3.0) becomes the criteria mean, which serves as the benchmark for the decision of a result being accepted or rejected.

It then means that any Table means ($\bar{x}$) that is 2.5 and above will be accepted, while the decision is rejected when the Table means is below the benchmark (2.5).

To obtain the Table mean, a variable is multiplied by its value, and the total figures are summed up, then divided by the total response rate.

Example 3.

CODE	SA	A	D	SD	X	DECISION
RESPONSE RATE	48	33	18	21	2.9	ACCEPTED
VALUES	X4	X3	X2	X1		

Source: Field survey (2023).

$$\text{Total} = 192 + 99 + 36 + 21$$

$$\text{Table Mean} = \text{Total} / \text{Response rate} = 348 / 120 = 2.9$$

This means that the decision is accepted because Table Mean ($\bar{x}$) is above the benchmark.

4.3 Demographic Data

In this study, one hundred and twenty questionnaires were administered to the staff of four business organizations, and the whole hundred were retrieved back. The analysis, therefore, is based on the response rate of one hundred and twenty (120) respondents, as presented below.

4.4 Bio-Data Information

Table (1-6) present the bio-data information of the respondents both in frequency and percentage.

Table 1: Sex of Response Table

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
FEMALE	75	62.5 %
MALE	45	37.5 %
TOTAL	120	100

Source: Field survey (2023).

Table (1) shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the sex of respondents. It shows that female respondents were more in number as 75 of them, representing 62.5%, answered and returned questionnaires, while the response of 45, accounting for 37.5%, was male.

4.5 Presentation and Discussion of Research Questions

The following tables present four research questions on a Likert 4-point rating scale. Three items were contained in each of the tables.

Table 5: Research Question One (1)

What are the business risks associated with database security?

ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	DECISION
Businesses suffer significant losses due to loopholes in the database	57	47	9	7	3.3	ACCEPTED
Customers/Clients develop trust issues for a business	70	36	7	7	3.4	ACCEPTED

organization with weak database security.						
Business incurred debt due to database hack	25	38	35	20	2.6	ACCEPTED

Source: Field survey (2023).

Table (5) above shows the mean score of the information gathered on business risks associated with database security. Three items were used to seek the respondent's assessment. All three items were accepted based on the benchmark for accepting or rejecting the decision. Item two has the highest acceptance, with a Table mean of 3.4. The decision, therefore, means that customers/clients develop trust issues for a business organization with weak database security. Item one follows the acceptance level with 3.4 as the Table mean. It confirms that businesses suffer significant losses as a result of loopholes in databases. Item three has a table mean of 2.6, which proves that the business incurred debt due to a database hack.

Table 6: Research Question Two (2)

Why is there need for database authentication?

ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	DECISION
It ensures the safety of the database	60	50	6	4	3.4	ACCEPTED
Database authentication prevents data from threats	29	49	34	8	2.8	ACCEPTED
It boasts business organization's confidence in the safety of their information	60	51	4	5	3.4	ACCEPTED

Source: Field survey (2023).

Table (6) above shows the mean score of the information gathered on the need for database authentication is shown. Three items were used for the assessment. The three

of them were accepted because the Table for each was above the benchmark set for a decision to be accepted or rejected. Item one in Table (6) has the highest acceptance level with a table mean of 3.4. This shows that database authentication guarantees the safety of the database. Item three follows with the Table mean of 3.4, which proves that database authentication boasts the confidence of business organizations in the safety of their information. The next item is item two, which has a table mean of 3.4, proving that database authentication prevents a database from all forms of threat.

Table 7: Research Question Three (3)

What are the security risks associated with a database?

ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	DECISION
Weak passwords and password sharing pose dangerous threats to the database	71	35	8	6	3.4	ACCEPTED
Corruption of data serves as a risk to the database	32	9	49	30	2.4	REJECTED
Lack of familiarity with technology poses a severe threat to database	32	60	18	10	3.0	ACCEPTED

Source: Field survey (2023).

The above Table (7) shows the information gathered from respondents on what constitutes security risks to the database. Three items were used to assess this information from the respondents, and out of three, two were accepted while one was rejected.

At the top of the acceptance, the level is item one in Table (7) with a Table mean of 3.4. It shows that weak passwords and password sharing significantly threaten database security. The next on the acceptance level is item three, with the Table mean of 3.0 proving that lack of familiarity with modern technology is a severe threat to database security. The rejected decision is item two, having a table mean of 2.4. The decision was rejected because the Table means it falls below the benchmark of (2.5) for

accepting the decision. This decision shows that data corruption does not pose any security threats to the database.

Table 8: Research Question four (4)

How can the maximum security of the database be ensured?

ITEM	SA	A	D	SD	X	DECISION
A strong password will ensure database security	72	39	4	5	3.5	ACCEPTED
Familiarity with modern technology by a business organization will ensure database protection.	46	65	5	4	3.3	ACCEPTED
Access to the internet will help secure databases in organizations	14	32	47	27	2.3	REJECTED

Source: Field survey (2023).

A strong password will help secure the data from an unauthorized individual gaining access to it. Item two on the Table follows on the acceptance level with that Table mean of 3.3, proving that familiarity with modern technology by business organizations will help provide maximum security of the database of such organization.

The rejected item came last on the Table with a table mean of 2.3. This shows that access to the Internet has nothing to do with the security of the database of any business organization.

4.6 Data Interpretation

Based on the themes of the data, the findings are presented in line with the study's research questions. This is presented below:

Research Question One: What are the business risks associated with database security?

In response to question one, the study's findings show that business organizations suffer significant losses due to database loopholes. This is because no individual or organization wants to partner with an organization that cannot secure vital information. The findings also show that customers and clients begin to doubt the credibility of the business organization suffering from database insecurity. Besides credibility issues, many clients will not trust such business organizations with their resources since it is difficult to secure their databases.

The findings also reveal that lacking database security can lead to business failure. This is because when it is difficult for business organizations to protect the information in their database, customers may begin to develop cold feet in transacting business with such an organization.

This finding agrees with (Saurabh & Siddhaling, 2012), who says that the success and failure of any business organization depend upon the quality, quantity, and level of security of a database.

Research Question Two: Why is there a need for database authentication?

This study finds that there is a great need for the authentication of the database. This is essential because database authentication helps to tighten the security of the database, thereby preventing unauthorized persons, which could be an internal threat, or hackers from gaining access to the information on the database either intentionally or accidentally.

The study also reveals that database authentication boosts the confidence of business organizations as they are sure that the information in their database is tightly secured from hackers. The findings also show that authentication ensures the confidentiality of the database; that is, only an authorized person can access the information in the database. This finding is in line with the findings of (Ali & Afzal, 2019), who say that only authorized users should be able to make any modifications to the database. This entails that no illegitimate person can access the database.

Research Question Three: What are the security risks to a database?

The research findings pointed out items that constitute risks to database security. This includes weak passwords and sharing of passwords. Sharing database passwords with a third party poses a dangerous threat to the database's safety. A third party with access to the database can readily temper the information by modifying or deleting some vital information. Weak passwords pose a risk to database security because they can easily be guessed by hackers or even internal threats who are not supposed to have access to such information. When a password is weak, anything can happen; it can easily be broken.

Research Question Four: How can the maximum security of the database be ensured?

It was discovered that strong passwords and data encryption would ensure the maximum security of a database. A strong password entails developing a firework password, like mixing numbers with the alphabet, so it becomes difficult to guess the password by hackers or unauthorized persons.

Data encryption gives a high level of security to data, and this is because encrypting data is difficult to read by an unauthorized person. A third party cannot easily understand data encryption, and this helps to provide maximum protection to the database. This finding agrees with the view of (Serban, 2012), who says that the purpose of encryption is to protect the confidentiality of the data and to maintain the data integrity of customers through the security services of the database.

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY

5.1 Summary of Finding

Database research has a long history, dating back more than 30 years. It has played a critical role in developing database systems, which have become an essential technology for many organizations. The database research field has explored various topics, including data modeling, query languages, database design, transaction management, and data storage and retrieval. Researchers in this field have developed numerous techniques and algorithms for improving database systems' performance, scalability, and reliability. This research has profoundly impacted how organizations manage and analyze their data, and it continues to be an active area of research and innovation today. Looking at the amount of data stored in a database and the importance of such data for any organization, the organization must secure the data in the database.

We can say that Database security is the use of a wide range of data security controls to protect databases against any attacks (internal or external).

The focus of this study was to assess database security in business organizations. In research question one, the study revealed that businesses suffer significant losses due to database security.

Research question two examined the need for database authentication. The study accepts it is the totality that authentication protects the database from threats as well as ensures its safety.

Research question three identified factors that constitute threats to database security. The study found that weak passwords, password sharing, and a lack of familiarity with modern technology constitute a risk to database security.

Research question four on how maximum protection of the database can be ensured. The study accepted that data encryption would provide maximum protection to database security.

5.2 Conclusion

Database security problems and research into various issues affecting business organizations were analyzed in this study. A comprehensive study on database security issues and their impact on businesses. Database security problems can vary depending on the type of database, the organization's size, the nature of the data being stored, and the level of security controls in place. Some common database security problems include:

- Unauthorized access: When attackers gain access to a database without proper authorization, they can steal, modify or delete sensitive information.
- Malware attacks: Malicious software, such as viruses, Trojans, or worms, can infect databases and cause damage or data loss.
- SQL injection attacks: Attackers can exploit vulnerabilities in SQL code to gain unauthorized access to a database or modify its content.
- Insider threats: Employees, contractors, or other trusted individuals with access to a database can intentionally or unintentionally cause data breaches by stealing, modifying, or deleting data.
- Weak or stolen credentials: Passwords or access keys that are weak or stolen can be used to gain unauthorized access to a database.

Research into these and other database security issues can help organizations better understand their risks and develop mitigation strategies. Some areas of research that can benefit businesses include:

- Threat intelligence: Studying the latest threats and attack techniques can help organizations stay ahead of attackers and prepare for potential threats.
- Access control: Developing effective access control policies and implementing robust authentication mechanisms can help prevent unauthorized access to databases.
- Encryption: Using encryption to protect data at rest and in transit can make it much harder for attackers to access and steal sensitive information.

- **Auditing and monitoring:** Implementing auditing and monitoring tools can help organizations detect and respond to security incidents in real time.

By analyzing these issues and researching effective security strategies, businesses can better protect their databases and ensure their sensitive data's confidentiality, integrity, and availability.

Organizations now depend on documents to decide about different business processes that will improve their bottom line. As a result, it is a smart idea to keep confidential details secure from prying eyes. Server security research papers have attempted to investigate the issues of potential assaults on database systems, such as loss of confidentiality and honesty. Because of the knowledge and volume of information in databases, they are the most common and straightforward targets for attackers. There are many options to accommodate a database. Today, there are several forms of attacks and threats against which a database should be secured. This paper discusses the decisions that must be made to protect personal data from attackers. It also goes into depth about how a loss of privacy can lead to extortion and humiliation in the workplace. This study, through its findings, discovered that database authentication is one of the ways to secure information in a database. Another method is to use an encryption strategy, which means the information is secured so that an unauthorized person or persons cannot access the information.

Based on findings, though limited by a few business organizations sampled, one would conclude that business organizations suffer immense losses due to database security issues.

5.3 Recommendation

From the discussion of findings, the following recommendation is made;

1. Business organizations should build strong passwords for their database to prevent an unauthorized person from gaining access.

2. Business organizations should not allow just anybody to be in charge of a database; they should scrutinize to an extent the person who will be in charge of the database in their organization.
3. Business organizations should invest in modern technology, train personnel, and familiarize themselves with technologies to protect their database. Investing in modern technology such as firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and data encryption tools can help protect databases from external and internal threats. Training personnel on using these tools effectively to protect the database is also essential.
4. Strong passwords: Using strong passwords and enforcing password policies can help prevent unauthorized access to databases. Passwords should be complex, unique, and changed regularly.
5. Scrutinize personnel: Businesses should conduct background checks and thoroughly vet individuals with access to sensitive data to ensure they are trustworthy and have no history of malicious behavior.

In addition to these recommendations, businesses should consider implementing access controls and limiting access to sensitive data to only those needing it. Regular security audits and risk assessments can also help identify vulnerabilities and ensure that security measures are up-to-date and effective.

By implementing these recommendations and taking a proactive approach to database security, businesses can reduce the risk of data breaches and protect their valuable assets and reputation.

5.4 Suggestion

Every research provides a platform for other researchers to build on, and there are still opportunities for further studies in database security in business organizations.

Firstly, conducting a similar study on other business organizations in other states in Nigeria can help validate this research's findings and determine if the same problems

prevail in other regions or industries. This can provide a broader perspective and help to identify common trends and issues across different organizations.

Secondly, there is a need for further research on how internal threats affect database security. This can include examining the role of insider threats, such as employees, contractors, and partners with authorized access to the database. The study can focus on identifying the causes and motivations of insider threats and developing effective strategies for mitigating such risks.

Finally, as technology continues to evolve, there is also a need for ongoing research to keep pace with the latest threats and trends in database security. This can involve exploring emerging technologies and their potential impact on database security, such as cloud computing, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT).

Overall, there is still a lot to learn about database security in organizations, and more study is required to create efficient risk reduction and data protection measures.

REFERENCE

- Abdullah, A. (2017). Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) Algorithm to Encrypt and Decrypt Data. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ako-Abdullah/publication/317615794_Advanced_Encryption_Standard_AES_Algorithm_to_Encrypt_and_Decrypt_Data/links/59437cd8a6fdccb93ab28a48/Advanced-Encryption-Standard-AES-Algorithm-to-Encrypt-and-Decrypt-Data.pdf
- Akanji, A. W., Elusoji, A. A., & Haastrup, A. V. (2014). A Comparative Study of Attacks on Databases and Database Security Techniques. *IEEE African Journal of Computing & ICT*, 7(5), 1-8. <https://afrijcict.net/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/vol-7-no-5-december-2014.pdf>
- Albalawi, U. (2018). Countermeasure of Statistical Inference in Database Security. *2018 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*, 2044-2047. <https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData.2018.8622241>
- Ali, A., & Afzal, M. (2016). Database Security: Threats and Solutions. *Int. J. Emerg. Technol. Adv. Eng.*, 6(2), 25-27.
- Arora, S., & Boaz, B. (2009). *Computational Complexity: A Modern Approach*. Cambridge University Press; Illustrated Edition. <https://theory.cs.princeton.edu/complexity/book.pdf>
- Asemah, E. S., Gujbawu, M., Ekhareafo, D. O., & Okpanachi, R. A. (2012). *Research Methods and Procedures in Mass Communication*. Jos: Great Future Press, Nigeria.
- Ashfaq, T., Khalid, R., Yahaya, A. S., Aslam, S., Azar, A. T., Alsafari, S., & Hameed, I. A. (2022). A Machine Learning and Blockchain Based Efficient Fraud Detection Mechanism. *Sensors (Basel)*, 22, 7162. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22197162>
- Babbie E. (2014). *The practice of social research* (14. ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Berg, J. R. (2009). *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences* (7th ed., pp. 101-157). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- Chandola, V., Banerjee, A., & Kumar, V. (2009). Anomaly Detection: A Survey. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 41(3), 1-58. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1541880.1541882>

- Choudhary, A. S. (2022, September 29). *Concept of Cryptography in Blockchain*. Analytics Vidhya. Retrieved April 17, 2023, from <https://www.analyticsvidhya.com/blog/2022/09/concept-of-cryptography-in-blockchain/>
- Chris Brook (2022, August 22). *What's the Cost of a Data Breach in 2019?* Digital Guardian. Retrieved April 15, 2023, from <https://www.digitalguardian.com/blog/whats-cost-data-breach-2019>
- Chris, H. (2018). *Literature Reviewing. Doing Your Literature Review. Releasing the Research Imagination*. (2nd ed.). London: Sage/OU.
- Coronel, C., & Morris, C. (2016). *Database Systems: Design, Implementation, & Management* (12th ed.). Cengage Learning. <https://books.google.com.ng/books?id=4JN4CgAAQBAJ>
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage. https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_609332/objava_105202/fajlovi/Creswell.pdf
- Crosby, M., Pattanayak, P., Verma, & Kalyanaraman, V. (2016). Blockchain technology: Beyond bitcoin. *Applied Innovation Review*, 2(6-10), 71-81. <https://scet.berkeley.edu/wp-content/uploads/AIR-2016-Blockchain.pdf>
- Crossman, A. (2020, March 19). *Understanding Purposive Sampling: An Overview of the Method and Its Applications*. ThoughtCo. Retrieved April 15, 2023, from <https://www.thoughtco.com/purposive-sampling-3026727>
- Deepika, N. S. (2015). Database Security: Threats and Security Techniques. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, 5(5), 621-624.
- Elmasri, R., & Navathe, S. B. (2015). *FUNDAMENTALS OF Database Systems* (7th ed.). Pearson. https://amirsmvt.github.io/Database/Static_files/Fundamental_of_Database_Systems.pdf
- Emil, B. (2009). Database Security - Attacks and Control Methods. *Journal of Applied Quantitative Methods*, 4(4), 449-454. http://www.jaqm.ro/issues/volume-4,issue-4/pdfs/jaqm_vol4_issue4.pdf
- Gall, M., Gall, J., & Borg, R. (2006). *Educational research: An introduction* (7th ed.). New York, NY: Pearson Education.

- GDPR (2016, April 27). *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (United Kingdom General Data Protection Regulation)*.
Legislation.gov.uk. Retrieved April 15, 2023, from <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/eur/2016/679/contents#>
- Gupta, B. B., Yamaguchi, S., & Agrawal, D. P. (2018). Advances in Security and Privacy of Multimedia Big Data in Mobile and Cloud Computing. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 77(7), 9203-9208. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-017-5301-x>
- Gupta, H., Mondal, S., Ray, S., Giri, B., Majundar, Dr., & Mishhra, V. P. (2019). Impact of SQL Injection in Database Security. *Conference: 2019 International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Knowledge Economy (ICCIKE)*, 296-299. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIKE47802.2019.9004430>
- Gupta, R.K. and Singh, P. (2013) A New Way to Design and Implementation of Hybrid CryptoSystem for Security of the Information in Public Network. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering*, 3, 2250-2459.
- Halpin, T., & Morgan, T. (2008). *Information Modeling and Relational Databases* (2nd ed.). Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc.
- Hashemi, S. (2013). Cloud Computing Technology: Security and Trust Challenges. *International Journal of Security, Privacy and Trust Management*, 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.5121/ijspmt.2013.2501>
- Hodge, V., & Austin, J. (2004). A Survey of Outlier Detection Methodologies. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 22(2), 85-126. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:AIRE.0000045502.10941.a9>
- IBM Security (n.d.). *Cost of a Data Breach Report in 2019*. IBM. Retrieved April 15, 2023, from <https://www.ibm.com/downloads/cas/RDEQK07R>
- Imran, S., & Hyder, S. (2009). Security Issues in Databases. *2009 Second International Conference on Future Information Technology and Management Engineering*, 541-545. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FITME.2009.140>
- Juma, J., & Makupi, D., Prof (2017). Understanding Database Security Metrics: A Review. *Mara International Journal of Scientific & Research Publications*, 1(1), 40-48. <http://repository.rongovarsity.ac.ke/handle/123456789/661>

- Kimball, R., & Ross, M. (2013). *The Data Warehouse Toolkit: The Definitive Guide to Dimensional Modeling* (3rd ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
https://aatinegar.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/Kimball_The-Data-Warehouse-Toolkit-3rd-Edition.pdf
- Kizza, J. M. (2017). *Guide to Computer Network Security* (5th ed.). Springer.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-55606-2>
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). Sample Size Determination. *Research Methodology. New Age International Publications, 1*, 74-81.
- Kshetri, N. (2020). Artificial intelligence in developing countries. *IEEE IT Professional, 22*(4), 63-68. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MITP.2019.2951851>
- Lin, A., & Chen, N. C. (2012). Cloud computing as an innovation: perception, attitude, and adoption. *International Journal of Information Management, 32*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2012.04.001>
- Liu, H., & Lang, B. (2019). Machine Learning and Deep Learning Methods for Intrusion Detection Systems: A Survey. *Applied Science, 9*(20), 4396.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/app9204396>
- Mahjabin, T., Xiao, Y., Sun, G., & Jiang, W. (2017). A survey of distributed denial-of-service attack, prevention, and mitigation techniques. *International Journal of Distributed Sensor Networks, 13*(12). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1550147717741463>
- Malik, A., Dhir, A., & Nieminen, M. (2016). Uses and Gratifications of digital photo sharing on Facebook. *Telematics and Informatics, 3*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2015.06.009>
- Malik, M., & Patel, T. (2016). Database Security - Attacks and Control Methods. *International Journal of Information Sciences and Techniques, 6*(1/2), 175-183. <https://doi.org/10.5121/ijist.2016.6218>
- Meseguer, J., & Montanari, U. (1990). Petri nets are monoids. *Information and Computation, 88*(2), 105-155. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0890-5401\(90\)90013-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0890-5401(90)90013-8)
- Mousa, A., Karabatak, M., & Mustafa, T. (2020, June 1). Database Security Threats and Challenges. *Conference: 2020 8th International Symposium on Digital Forensics and Security (ISDFS, 3*(5), 810-813.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ISDFS49300.2020.9116436>
- Nassif, A., Abu Talib, M., Nasir, Q. R., & Dakalbab, F. (2021). Machine Learning for Anomaly Detection: A Systematic Review. *IEEE Access*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3083060>

- Nedhal, A. S. A., & Dana, A., Prof (2013). Database Security Threats: A Survey Study. *5th International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology (CSIT)*, 5, 60-64.
- Odirichukwu, J., & Asagba, P. (2017). Security Concept in Web Database Development and Administration — A Review Perspective. *2017 IEEE 3rd International Conference Electro-Technology National Development NIGERCON 2017*, 383-391.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/NIGERCON.2017.8281910>
- Ohaja, E.U. (2003). Mass communication research and project report writing. Lagos: John Letterman Limited.
- Ojo, O. (2003). Fundamental of research methods. Lagos: Nelson Clemmy Press.
- Oracle. (n.d.). Oracle database encryption. Retrieved March 29, 2023, from <https://www.oracle.com/database/technologies/security/advanced-security/database-encryption.html>
- Paul, P. K., & Aithal, P. S. (2019). Database Security: An Overview and Analysis of Current Trend. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 4(2), 53- 58. <http://doi.org/10.5281/>
- Paul, P. K., & Aithal, S. (2019, October 18). Database Security: An Overview and Analysis of Current Tren. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences*, 4(2), 53-58.
<https://doi.org/10.47992/IJMTS.2581.6012.0070>
- Pevnev, V., & Kapchynskiy, S. (2018). Database Security: Threats and Preventive Measures. *Advanced Information Systems*, 2, 69-72.
<https://doi.org/10.20998/2522-9052.2018.1.13>
- Sarmah, S. S. (2019). Database Security –Threats & Prevention. *International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology*, 67(5), 46-53.
<https://doi.org/10.14445/22312803/IJCTT-V67I5P108>
- Saurabh, K., & Siddhaling, U., Dr (2012). Review of Attacks on Databases and Database Security Techniques. *Facility International Journal of Engineering Technology and Database Security Techniques Research*, 2(11), 1-7.
- Şerban, M. (2012). Methods to Increase Search Performance for Encrypted Databases. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 3, 1063-1068.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(12\)00274-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(12)00274-2)

- Sharma, M., Chaudhary, N., & Sagar, K. (2018). An Introduction of Theory of Computation. *International Journal of Recent Trends in Engineering & Research*. <https://doi.org/10.23883/ijrter.2018.4156.axkvi>
- Sharma, P. (2016). Database Security: Attacks and Technique. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 7(12), 313-319.
- Shikha, R., & Shanky, R. (2016). Data Security in Cloud Computing Using Various Encryption Techniques. *International Journal of Modern Computer Science (IJMCS)*, 4(3), 163-166.
- Shivnandan, S., & Rakesh, K. R. (2014). Review on Security Threats on Database. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, 5(3).
- Singh, S., & Rai, R. K. (2014, May 1). A Review Report on Security Threats on Database. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, 5(3), 3215-3219. <https://ijcsit.com/docs/Volume%205/vol5issue03/ijcsit20140503118118.pdf>
- Singh, S., & Rai, R.K. (2014). A Review on Security Threats on Database. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, 5(3).
- Stallings, W. (2015). *Cryptography and network security: Principles and practice* (7th ed.). Pearson. <https://dl.hiva-network.com/Library/security/Cryptography-and-network-security-principles-and-practice.pdf>
- Stam, H. (2007). Theoretical psychology. In *The international handbook of psychology*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. <http://doi.org/10.4135/9781848608399>
- Swan, M. (2015). *Blockchain: Blueprint for a new economy*. O'Reilly Media, Inc.
- Swati, J., & Dimple, C. (2020). A Relative Study on Different Database Security Threats and their Security Techniques. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11657.60000>
- Tabrizchi, H., & Rafsanjani, M. K. (2020, October 1). A survey on security challenges in cloud computing: Issues, threats, and solutions. *The Journal of Supercomputing*, 76(12), 9493–9532. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-020-03213-1>

- Taherdoost, H. (2023). Smart Contracts in Blockchain Technology: A Critical Review. *Information. MDPI*, 14(2), 117.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/info14020117>
- Teimoor, R. A. (2021, October 10). A Review of Database Security Concepts, Risks, and Problems. *UHD Journal of Science and Technology*, 5(2), 38-46.
<https://doi.org/10.21928/uhdjst.v5n2y2021.pp38-46>
- Tejumaiye, J. A. (2003). *Mass Communication Research: An Introduction*. Ibadan: Scepter Prints. <https://ir.unilag.edu.ng/handle/123456789/10073>
- Thilina (2020). A Study on Cloud Security Concerns and Resolutions.
- Thomas, J. R., & Nelson, J. K. (2001). *Research Methods in Physical Activity* (4th ed., pp. 1-449). Human Kinetics.
- Tian, Y., Wang, Z., Xiong, J., & Ma, J. (2020). A Blockchain-Based Secure Key Management Scheme With Trustworthiness in DWSNs. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 16(6), 6193-6202.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2020.2965975>
- Tipton, H.F., & Krause, M. (2007). *Information Security Management Handbook* (6th ed.). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781439833032>
- Toshniwal, A., Mahesh, K., & Jayashree, R. R. (2020). Overview of Anomaly Detection techniques in Machine Learning. *Applied Science*, 9, 808-815.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/I-SMAC49090.2020.9243329>
- Tresorit Team (2019, July 29). *The Top 6 Takeaways from The 2019 Cost of a Data Breach Report*. Tresorit. Retrieved April 15, 2023, from <https://tresorit.com/blog/the-top-6-takeaways-from-the-2019-cost-of-a-data-breach-report/>
- Vehovar, V., Toepoel, V., & Steinmetz, S. (2016). *Non-probability sampling* (pp. 329-346). SAGE.
- Wang, L. Y., Hu, H. H., Wang, L., & Qin, J. Q. (2022). Privacy assurances and social sharing in social commerce: The mediating role of threat-coping appraisals. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 67.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2022.103028>
- White Paper (2016.). *The Top 5 Database Security Threats*. Imperva.
<https://www.imperva.com/resources/resource-library/white-papers/the-top-5-database-security-threats/>

Yan, S. Y. (1998). *Introduction to Formal Languages and Machine Computation* (pp. 155-156). World Scientific Publishing Company.

<https://www.perlego.com/book/846078/introduction-to-formal-languages-and-machine-computation-an-pdf>

Yassine, H., Aya, S., Abdullah, A., Faycal, B., Abbas, A. T., Iraklis, V., Magdalini, E., Christos, S., & George, D. (2022). Blockchain-based recommender systems: Applications, challenges and future opportunities. *Computer Science Review*, 43, 7162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2021.100439>

APPENDIX I
LETTER OF REQUEST FOR PARTICIPATION

6, Olusanya Coker Close,
Paiko, Idimu,
Lagos State.
Nigeria.

Dear Respondent,

My name is Benedict Joseph Oluwaseun, a student of the School Of Architecture, Computing, and Engineering - ACE, at the University Of East London, studying for the degree of Master of Science in Information Security and Digital Forensics.

I hereby solicit your cooperation to provide relevant information on my research topic: "An Appraisal of database security in business organizations".

Kindly note that all information provided will be treated with confidentiality and will be used for academic purposes.

Yours faithfully,
Joseph Benedict

QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION A

BIO-DATA INFORMATION

Please tick () against the right option in the space (s) provided:

Sex: Male () Female ()

Job Role...

SECTION B

The following questions were measured basically on direction and intensity. You are to tick only one box to take a stand. The options are

SA -----Strongly Agreed

A----- Agreed

D -----Disagreed

SD ----- Strongly Disagreed

Research Question One (1):

What are the business risks associated with database security?

ITEM	SA	A	D	SD
Businesses suffer significant losses due to loopholes in the database				
Customers/Clients develop trust issues for a business organization with weak database security.				
Business incurred debt due to database hack				

Research Question Two (2):

Why is the need for database authentication?

ITEM	SA	A	D	SD
It ensures the safety of the database				
Database authentication prevents data from threats				
It boasts business organization's confidence in the safety of their information				

Research Question Three (3):

What are the security risks associated with a database?

ITEM	SA	A	D	SD
Weak passwords and password sharing pose dangerous threats to the database				
Corruption of data serves as a risk to the database				
Lack of familiarity with technology poses a serious threat to the database				

Research Question Four (4):

How can the maximum security of the database be ensured?

ITEM	SA	A	D	SD
A strong password will ensure database security				
Familiarity with modern technology by a business organization will ensure database protection.				
Access to the internet will help secure databases in organizations				